

Deep Relative Learning for Prediction of Preclinical Alzheimer’s Disease

Nupur Thakur¹, Riti Paul¹, Baoxin Li^{*1}, Oana Dumitrescu², Yuxiang Zhou²

¹ Arizona State University, Tempe, Arizona, USA
{nsthaku1, rpaul12, baoxin.li}@asu.edu

² Mayo Clinic, Phoenix, Arizona, USA
{dumitrescu.oana, zhou.yuxiang}@mayo.edu

Abstract. Alzheimer’s disease (AD) is the most common form of dementia that primarily affects elderly individuals, gradually impairing their memory and cognitive abilities. As the disease progresses, Alzheimer’s patients often experience a decline in their ability to perform mundane tasks. Numerous studies have shown intervening during the preclinical stage of AD holds significant promise for mitigating its advancement. However, identifying preclinical AD cases presents a major challenge as such patients exhibit minimal to no detectable neurodegeneration, and therefore generally classified as ‘cognitively normal’. Given the difficulty of detecting these subtle alterations through unaided human eye, we propose a novel approach called Relative Scoring Network (**RSNet**), which integrates relative learning and contrastive learning to detect preclinical AD patients based solely on their MRI scans. RSNet also produces a score that can be used to aid clinicians in gauging the severity of preclinical AD. We demonstrate the feasibility of the idea and its potential, especially the differentiation between healthy individuals and those in the preclinical stage of AD, utilizing the OASIS-3 dataset.

Keywords: Preclinical Alzheimer’s Disease · Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) · Deep Learning · Relative Learning · Contrastive Learning

1 Introduction

Alzheimer’s Disease (AD), a neurodegenerative disorder, is typically classified into three stages: preclinical, mild cognitive impairment (MCI), and Alzheimer’s dementia. While significant progress has been made in utilizing computer vision techniques to detect advanced stages (stage 2 and 3) of dementia [2], the detection of preclinical AD is largely underexplored [1]. This research gap is primarily due to the absence of symptoms and minimal signs of neurodegeneration in preclinical AD patients. In contrast to existing approaches [1], we propose an innovative scoring approach, **Relative Scoring Network (RSN)** that operates on the principle of learning the differences in the MRI of patients in different stages of AD. The purpose of this score is two-fold - 1) to distinguish between

* Corresponding author.

the challenging distinction between cognitively normal individuals and those in the preclinical stage of AD through a scoring mechanism; 2) to aid clinicians in ascertaining the severity of preclinical AD, which holds significant importance as early intervention can greatly impact patients' quality of life.

2 RSNet: Proposed Method

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed approach, Relative Scoring Network (RSNet).

Our method operates on the hypothesis that AD markers tend to become more pronounced in later preclinical AD stages, driving us to develop RSNet which learns such common patterns using deep relative learning. We define the goal of RSNet to produce $s \in \{0, 1\}$ representing a relative score of the degree of preclinical AD severity, given the MRI input represented by $X = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_N\}$ where $X_i \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 1 \times H \times W}$ and N, M, W, H is the total number of MRI scans, number of slices, height and width of each slice respectively. The overview of the RSNet is presented in Fig. 1. X is passed through a 3D-CNN to generate $X^f \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d}$ where d is the embedding dimension, which is passed to the scoring network to yield a score s for every input. For RSNet training, we use $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{rs} + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{ce}$ where λ maintains a balance between the relative score loss \mathcal{L}_{rs} , and the contrastive latent embedding loss \mathcal{L}_{ce} .

We define $\mathcal{L}_{rs} = \|\phi - \tilde{\phi}\|^2$ where $\phi = s_i - s_j, i, j = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, n is the number of samples in a batch and $\tilde{\phi}$ are the pseudo target scores. Assuming three classes - cognitively normal, preclinical AD and advanced AD, we form two types of pairs within a batch to define $\tilde{\phi}$. For positive pairs (samples belonging to the same category), we set $\tilde{\phi} = \gamma_1, \gamma_1 \approx 0$ as intra-class score variation should be low. For negative pairs (samples belonging to the same category), $\tilde{\phi} \approx 1$ except the preclinical AD versus advanced AD case where it should be low so RSNet can learn their similarities. So, $\tilde{\phi} = \gamma_2, \gamma_2 \approx 1$ except for preclinical versus advanced AD case where we set $\gamma_2 \approx 0.2$. To make RSNet robust to variations in $\tilde{\phi}$, we sample γ_1, γ_2 from $U(\gamma_i - \alpha, \gamma_i)$ where $\alpha \approx 0.1$. Note that $\tilde{\phi}$ is not an absolute difference to enforce $s_n < s_p < s_a$ where s_n, s_p, s_a are the RSNet scores for healthy, preclinical AD and advanced AD categories.

To further support \mathcal{L}_{rs} , we apply contrastive learning-based loss in the latent space, $\mathcal{L}_{ce} = \log(1 + \sum_{p=1}^K \exp(\beta(X_i^f X_p^{f-}))) \sum_{q=1}^O \exp(-\beta(X_i^f X_q^{f+}))$ where β is

the scaling parameter for X_f , K and O are the number of negative and positive samples respectively. \mathcal{L}_{ce} brings the embedding vectors from the same category closer and pushes them away from embeddings of other categories, which enhances the relative score learning mechanism.

3 Experiment Results

We present our preliminary results on the OASIS-3 [3] dataset using the SWI MRI volumes. For all 72 slices, we resize to 128×128 and then a random crop of 96×96 . The data is split based on patient IDs - Train: 603/23/124; Validation: 86/3/18, Test: 172/7/18 where $././.$ is the number of samples in cognitively normal class, preclinical AD, and advanced AD respectively.

Set	s_n^{avg} (\downarrow)	s_p^{avg} (\uparrow)	s_a^{avg} (\uparrow)
Validation	0.49	0.61	0.69
Test	0.46	0.58	0.72

Table 1. Average score from RSNet on validation and test data of OASIS-3.

The 3D-CNN consists of 3 convolutional blocks and each of them has a convolutional layer, instance normalization, ReLU, and max pooling layer. The scoring network has 2 stacked fully connected layers. Table 1 shows our results for the average RSNet scores for each class where a noticeable trend emerges - $s_n^{avg} < s_p^{avg} < s_a^{avg}$ indicating RSNet can discern between preclinical AD and others by leveraging deep relative learning.

4 Conclusion & Future Work

We introduce RSNet to generate a preclinical AD severity score by leveraging the relative distinctions in neurodegeneration among patients at various AD stages. Through preliminary experiments, we demonstrate the viability and potential of RSNet in discerning between preclinical AD and others. Further refinement of these findings can be achieved by incorporating non-imaging clinical data like age and genetic information with MRI data. This would provide more information to improve the precision of predicting the preclinical AD severity levels, thus helping clinicians in the early detection and facilitating appropriate interventions.

References

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